

DURABILITY OF FIBERS IN AGGRESSIVE ALKALINE ENVIRONMENT

A. Coricciati (1), P. Corvaglia (2), G. Mosheyev

(1) Department of Materials and Structures Engineering, Consorzio CETMA
S.S. 7 km 706+030, 72100 Brindisi, Italy

(2) BG Polymers

M.P. South Lachish, 79370 Kibbutz Beit Guvrin, Israel

angela.coricciati@cetma.it ; paolo.corvaglia@cetma.it ; gregory@bgpol.co.il

SUMMARY

Fiber Reinforced Plastics (FRPs) are innovative materials that are going to replace some traditional structural strengthening techniques. Evaluating durability of composite materials in aggressive environments is basic for long-term performances assessment. In this study aging tests were made on glass and basalt fibers in alkaline environment.

Keywords: Durability, alkali, fibers, glass, basalt.

INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in civil applications spread during last years, thanks of their many advantages such as low weight, high strength-to-weight ratio, ease of handling, drapability, speed of installation, low thickness and visual impact, reversibility. Nevertheless, the problem of durability could appear if fibers are introduced in aggressive environments, such as the concrete ones for civil applications. In this case, the high concentration of alkali ions is the main cause of fibers damage. Particularly, weight loss and reduction in mechanical properties could appear. In the technical literature different studies are present, but the reported results appear somewhat contrasting. For these reasons, in this study, accelerated conditioning in alkali environment was carried out on different types of fibers, in order to comparatively evaluate their weight loss and their tensile strength reduction. The investigated fibers were ordinary E-glass, a boron-free type of E-glass (trade name Advantex), AR-glass and basalt. Basalt fibers are very promising thanks to their fire resistance, due to their magmatic origin, good mechanical properties and relatively low cost. On the other hand, they are still not very studied, being a relatively new kind of fibers. The effectiveness of an acrylic copolymer coating, with lowered water absorption, specifically formulated to improve the alkali resistance, was also evaluated.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS ABOUT FRP DURABILITY IN ALKALINE ENVIRONMENT

A careful analysis of different scientific papers dealing with glass and basalt fibers behaviour in aggressive alkaline environments was carried out. A summarizing wrap-up

of the various results obtained through different test conditions is shown in the following lines. For glass fibers it is important to underline how pH level influences GFRP degradation [1]. In fact, it was found that, in concrete environment, when pH becomes lower, GFRP degradation drops, too [1]. Besides, a pH reduction of 10% from its initial value was measured after six years, so that it can be concluded that GFRP degradation should appear in the earlier years of structure life [2]. Moreover, an absence of GFRP degradation was noticed when fibers are well protected by a particular type of polymeric matrix [1, 2]. Other tests under a constant tensile load were made on E-glass and on boron-free Advantex-glass rods in aggressive conditions (Portland cement) applied during the loading, both at room temperature and at 60 °C [3]. It seemed that Advantex-glass showed the best corrosion behaviour after aggressive treatment, while E-glass had a greater reduction in mechanical properties. Besides, high temperature (60°C) caused a more considerable loss of strength both in E-glass and in Advantex-glass. The presence of some coatings (like multi-walled carbon nanotubes or organoclay surface nanostructured) on E-glass and AR-glass can improve fiber strength both on unconditioned and conditioned specimens, even if the values of strength obtained after the aggressive treatment (5 wt% NaOH for 7 days) were lower than those obtained for unconditioned ones. Moreover, while coated fibers did not change their diameter, uncoated fibers changed their aspect and showed a greater surface roughness [4]. In another work [5], accelerated tests were made using high temperature, which increased the effect of a particular aggressive environment, and an alkaline solution. It was found that GFRP rods had a good behaviour if well coated by the matrix, except with a polyester resin, which had a low resistance in basic solutions. Similar results were obtained in another paper [6], where accelerating effect of temperature was underlined again, even if the aggressive solutions considered were various. Besides, in pull-out test performed on GFRP rods embedded in concrete, bars set in normal concrete failed because of bond failure, while bars embedded in high performance concrete failed for concrete splitting. High temperature and aggressive environment accelerated the reduction of bond strength. Accelerated tests on GFRP immersed in different types of concrete environments are described in [7]. Besides, the flexural strength becomes lower after long time exposure and if high temperature are used. The highest values of strength reduction appeared in composites with a low number of layers and with the highest time of exposure. Fiber surface pitting and roughness increase, which reduced mechanical properties, could be seen in aged specimens. Another paper [8] analyzes rods behaviour in alkaline solution: the reduction of both tensile and bond strength (measured by pull-out tests) was higher when long exposure time and high temperature were used. AR-glass behaviour in concrete environment is studied in [9]: its resistance reduced in concrete characterized by high pH value, while it remained almost constant in concrete with neutral pH. At last, paper [10] compared E-glass and AR-glass behaviour under the same concrete exposure using also high temperature. The reduction of AR-glass strength after 4 days was of about 7.4%, while for E-glass it was of about 84.2%; the ultimate strain reduction, measured after 7 days, was of about 38% for AR-glass and of about 60% for E-glass.

For basalt fibers there are discordant indications in technical papers about their behaviour after aging treatments. In one paper [11], tensile and short-beam tests were made on glass and basalt fibers after treatment for 150 days in saturated sodium chloride solution: it was evidenced the better interlaminar behaviour of basalt fibers in comparison to glass fibers. Besides, a little reduction of Young Modulus appeared both

in E-glass and in basalt fibers because of a possible interfacial degradation. Other tests (1M NaOH for 7, 14, 21 and 28 days at $T=40^{\circ}\text{C}$) were made on glass, basalt and carbon fibers [12]: while carbon fibers kept their integrity, glass and basalt ones lost their volumes significantly under alkali condition. It was then concluded that glass and basalt fibers showed the same high reduction in volume and in mechanical properties. On the contrary, a contrasting result, in term of weight loss, is reported in another paper [13]: after boiling in cement saturated solution for 3 hours, a weight loss of 4.5%, 0.35% and 0.15% appeared for E-glass, basalt and AR-glass, respectively. Another paper [14] deals with basalt fibers behaviour in aggressive environments (2mol/l NaOH) in boiled water for 3 hours. While its weight loss was of about 4%, its strength reduction was of about 18%. Besides, SEM images showed the presence of diffused micro-cracks on fibers surface and EDS analysis evidenced a variation in chemical composition before and after aging. Aging tests on composites were made using alkaline solution and different times of exposure: a flexural strength reduction of about 22% appears on basalt fibers after 30 days of exposure, while flexural modulus remained the same until 90 days of exposure.

From the analyzed literature, we can conclude that boron-free E-glass and AR glass show a better behaviour after aggressive conditioning in concrete environment, in comparison to ordinary E-glass. For basalt fibers, instead, there are contrasting results: one of the papers [12] affirms that both E-glass and basalt fibers show the same volume (of 70%) and strength (of 80%) reduction after 28 days of conditioning in NaOH solution. Another one [13], instead, affirm that basalt weight loss is much lower than glass weight loss.

TESTS AND RESULTS

After a careful scientific research, accelerated aging tests were made to evaluate the weight loss and the decrease of mechanical properties of glass and basalt fibers, in order to quantify their performance limits.

Accelerated aging in alkaline solution

The fibers analyzed are basalt and three types of glass fibers: ordinary E-glass, boron-free E-glass (trade name Advantex) and AR-glass. The pattern chosen for the fabrics is unidirectional in order to evaluate better the mechanical properties of fibers. Besides, the fabrics have the same surface density (300 g/m^2), in order to have a more direct comparison of the possible weight loss of the different types of fibers. The standard test method used for the accelerated aging test in alkaline solution is the one described in ASTM E 2098-00 [15]. The test consists of immersing the specimens in a 5% (50 g/l; $\text{pH}=14$) sodium hydroxide aqueous solution (in distilled water) for 28 days in tight containers in order to avoid any evaporative loss, at temperature of $22^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. The specimens have to be straight during all the test and the solution level is marked on the container, in order to monitor possible evaporation. After conditioning, specimens are well rinsed in distilled water and dried for 7 days in the same controlled laboratory conditions.

Weight loss

The specimens weight was measured both before and after the aging in order to evaluate fibers weight loss. The main results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Weight loss of the different fibers after aging

Fiber type	Number of specimens	Weight loss [%]
E-glass	12	<i>Average value</i> 3.87
		<i>St. Dev.</i> 0.57
Boron-free E-glass	12	<i>Average value</i> 3.00
		<i>St. Dev.</i> 0.94
AR-glass	6	<i>Average value</i> 2.01
		<i>St. Dev.</i> 0.32
basalt	12	<i>Average value</i> 1.04
		<i>St. Dev.</i> 0.44

It is interesting to underline that E-glass fibers presented the greatest weight loss, of 3.87% (as average value), while basalt fibers presented the lowest one, of 1.04% (Figure 1). Statistical test (“Student test”) was made in order to understand if the four average values of the weight loss belonged to the same statistical population. It was found that the differences between the average values are significant for all the possible combinations: so, they are not due to the experimental data dispersion.

Figure 1: Average value of weight loss (%) of the different fibers

Tensile tests

After the aging in alkali solution, tensile tests were made in order to evaluate the maximum load P_{max} and the ultimate tensile strain of all the fibers before and after the aging, comparing the values obtained for both reference (not conditioned) and conditioned specimens. ASTM D 3039/D 3039M – 00 [16] is the Standard Test Method used. Laminates were made through hand lay-up technology, which consists of applying resin and fibers on a mould and then of removing air bubbles through a roller. The matrix used was an epoxy resin (*MapeWrap 31*, from *MAPEI*) and the laminates were produced using one ply of unidirectional fabrics. After one day curing at room temperature, a post-cure at 40 °C for 4 hours was made in order to permit the

completion of polymerization. Due to the difficulty in controlling the amount of resin in manual wet lay-up process, the cross-section area was not considered significant in these tests and all the results were referred only to the maximum load (taking into account that, in unidirectional composites, nearly the whole contribution to longitudinal properties are given by fibers) and to ultimate strain; nevertheless, this is not a severely limiting issue, as the tests have only comparative purpose between conditions before and after aging.

Table 2: Mechanical properties for each type of fibers before and after aging

Sample	Ultimate strain [%]	St. dev.	Percentage reduction [%]	Ultimate load [N]	St. dev.	Percentage reduction [%]
EGR	2.09	0.16	57	3280	280.12	58
EGC	0.89	0.07		1364	137.21	
BfEGR	2.12	0.17	47	3238	336.78	48
BfEGC	1.13	0.11		1684	96.40	
ARGR	2.14	0.12	24	3978	214.29	27
ARGC	1.63	0.13		2898	292.18	
BR	2.72	0.25	74	3990	358.33	74
BC	0.72	0.14		1043	145.91	

EG = E-glass; **BfEG** = Boron free E-glass; **ARG** = AR-glass; **B** = basalt; **R** =Reference; **C** = Conditioned

Figure 2: Average maximum load (P_{max}) decrease

From these results, it can be seen that AR-glass fibers present the better mechanical behaviour after aging. In fact, the maximum load decreases of about 27%, and the ultimate tensile strain of about 24%. On the contrary, basalt fibers present the worst mechanical properties after the aggressive conditioning. In fact, the maximum load decreases of about 74%, as well as the ultimate strain. E-glass and Advantex-glass fibers show an intermediate behaviour. Besides, we can notice that ultimate tensile strain decrease shows the similar trend of maximum load decrease in all the fiber types, so that we can focus our attention only on weight loss and P_{max} decrease. As to the failure modes, while the reference specimens failed with the presence of splitting and of

a little delamination, the conditioned specimens failed with a sudden crack, without delamination and splitting. E-glass probably shows the greater weight loss because it is more chemically reactive with the alkaline solution, having a larger number of silicate tetrahedrals, in comparison to basalt fibers. These last ones, in fact, come from the extrusive basic magmas, which are characterized by a lower concentration of SiO₂ (of about 45÷50%) groups in comparison to glass composition. Despite their lower weight loss in comparison to glass fibers, basalt fibers exhibited the highest reduction in mechanical properties. This is probably due to the crystallographic structure of basalt, which is made by olivine (single tetrahedron), pyroxenes (linear chain) and plagioclase (tetrahedral space structure). In fact, alkaline aggressive environment can break some bonds of the linear tetrahedral chain of pyroxenes, so that a greater strength reduction can be seen. On the contrary, when alkaline ions break some bonds in a three-dimensional network of silicates (such as the glass amorphous structures), the final strength can be less invalidated, due to a lower damage sensibility of a three-dimensional structure with respect to a linear structure. Moreover, Fe can react with O₂, causing the formation of reaction products (oxides), which can reduce strength not changing the weight. Besides, some cations of the solution (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺) could freely bind to fibers silicate structures. For example, Na⁺ can substitute Ca²⁺ in the same position of the network because these two atoms have comparable dimensions. The cations exchange could affect the network of basalt, varying its mechanical and chemical properties, but not varying the weight.

Accelerated aging of the fabrics covered by the protective coating in alkaline solution

Accelerated aging tests in alkaline aggressive solution were repeated with the same procedure described previously, but using a coating, developed by BG Polymers to improve the alkali resistance of the fibers. This coating is B.G. POL SA-2375, a styrene acrylic copolymer emulsion designed for use as a binder in water based paints, exterior texture finishes, and flexible roof coating compounds (Table 3).

Table 3: Coating properties

Solids content	50 ± 1 %
Viscosity at 25°C Brookfield LVT 3/12	3000 – 7000 cps
pH	7.5 -8.5
Particle size	Approx. 0.15 – 0.25 μm
Specific Gravity at 25 °C	1.02
Surfactant Type	Anionic/Nonionic
Freeze/Thaw Stability	Unstable
Minimum Film Formation Temperature	+ 9 °C
Tg	10 °C

The coating was applied on three types of fibers (E-glass, AR-glass and basalt) and it was diluted in water with a dilution ratio of 1:1. The cut fabrics were weighed, drowned in the diluted solution and, successively, dried in air. After the application of the coating, the fabrics were weighed again (in order to measure the weight increase of the fabrics, due to the application of the coating), and aged in the aggressive alkaline solution. After accelerated aging, weight loss tests on fibers were not performed, because it would be impossible to distinguish between the weight loss due to the coating and the one due to the fibers. On the other hand, tensile tests were carried out in order to understand the real condition of the fibers after the aggressive treatment. The specimens for the tensile tests were produced through hand lay-up technology, using the same epoxy resin of previous tests and one ply of fabric. Besides, the variation of both the ultimate tensile strain and the maximum load were evaluated (Table 4).

Table 4: Mechanical properties for each type of fibers before and after aging

Sample	Ultimate strain [%]	St. dev.	Percentage reduction [%]	Ultimate load [N]	St. dev.	Percentage reduction [%]
EGR	1.94	0.24	33	2760	204.33	36
EGC	1.29	0.05		1758	81.67	
ARGR	1.51	0.18	25	2440	484.97	21
ARGC	1.14	0.24		1934	139.75	
BR	2.14	0.21	31	2928	334.47	40
BC	1.47	0.08		1764	159.31	

EG = E-glass; **ARG** = AR-glass; **B** = basalt; **R** =Reference; **C** = Conditioned

From these results it is clear how AR-glass fibers showed the best aging behaviour, in comparison with E-glass and basalt fibers.

Comparison between aging tests made on fabrics with and without the coating

The effectiveness of the coating was evaluated comparing the results obtained from the aging tests made on fabrics with and without the coating (Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5).

Figure 3: Mechanical properties of E-glass fibers with and without the coating, before and after the aging

Figure 4: Mechanical properties of AR-glass fibers with and without the coating, before and after the aging

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of basalt fibers with and without the coating, before and after the aging

Comparing corresponding results in Table 2 and Table 4 we can state that the reduction of mechanical properties due to aging is smaller when the coating is used. Nevertheless,

the coating showed a somewhat contrasting effect on E-glass and on basalt fibers. In fact, while it improves the alkali resistance of the fibers aged in an aggressive alkaline solution, at the same time it reduces the strength of the reference (unconditioned) fibers, probably because of a “sheath effect” (there is a not perfect fibers impregnation by the matrix). Hence, we can conclude that the coating is advisable, for E-glass and basalt fibers, only if considerable alkaline aging is expected. On the other hand, there is no point in using the coating if the fibers are made of AR-glass.

CONCLUSIONS

In this experimental study, accelerated aging tests in alkaline solution were carried out in order to evaluate glass (ordinary E-glass, boron-free E-glass and AR-glass) and basalt fibers durability when exposed to alkaline aggressive environment, such as the concrete one. Particularly, weight loss and reduction of mechanical properties were evaluated. Besides, the effectiveness of an acrylic coating in improving the alkali resistance of the fibers was studied. As expected, in absence of the coating, the best behaviour, in terms of both weight loss and reduction of mechanical properties, is shown by AR-glass fibers. The coating, although reducing the mechanical properties of not-aged E-glass and basalt fibers, showed a good protective effect when considerable alkaline aging is present.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was carried out in the framework of the Project POLYTECT (Polyfunctional Technical Textiles against Natural Hazards), financed by the E.U. Commission under the 6th F.P. The authors acknowledge the European Commission for the financial support granted to the project.

References

1. Boulfiza M., Banthia N. (2005), “Studies of GFRP Durability in Cores obtained from ISIS Field Demonstration Projects” - *University of Saskatchewan and University of British Columbia*.
2. Onofrei M. (2005), “Durability of GFRP reinforced concrete from field demonstration structures” – *University of Manitoba*.
3. Renaud C. M., et Greenwood M. E., “Effect of Glass Fibers and Environments on Long-Term Durability of GFRP Composites”.
4. Gao S. L., Mäder E. et Plonka R. (2007), “Nanostructured coatings of glass fibers: Improvement of alkali resistance and mechanical properties”, *Acta Materialia*, Vol 55, pp. 1043-1052.
5. Micelli F. et Nanni A. (2004), “Durability of FRP rods for concrete structures”, *Construction and Building Materials*, Vol. 18, pp. 491-503.
6. Chen Y., Davalos J. F., Ray I. et Kim H. (2005), “Accelerated aging tests for evaluations of durability performance of FRP reinforcing bars for concrete structures”, *Composite Structures*, Vol. 78, pp. 101-111.

7. Karbhari V. M., Murphy K. Et Zhang S. (2002), "Effect of concrete based alkali solutions on short-term durability of E-glass/vinylester composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 36, pp. 2101-2121.
8. Abbasi A. et Hogg P. J. (2005), "Temperature and environmental effects on glass fibre rebar: modulus, strength and interfacial bond strength with concrete", *Composites Part B: engineering*, Vol. 36, pp. 394-404.
9. Cuypers H., Wastiels J., Van Itterbeeck P. V., De Bolster E., Orłowsky J. et Raupach M. (2006), "Durability of glass fibre reinforced composites experimental methods and results", *Composites, Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, Vol. 37, pp. 207-215.
10. Saint-Gobain Reinforcements, "Why use Alkali Resistant Glass for reinforcing concrete?".
11. Liu Q., Giffard H. S., Shaw M. T., Parnas R. S. et McDonnell A., "Preliminary Investigation of Basalt Fiber Composite Properties for Application in Transportation".
12. Sim J., Park C. et Moon D. Y. (2005), "Characteristics of basalt fiber as a strengthening material for concrete structures", *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 36, pp. 504-512.
13. Kamenny Vek – Advanced basalt fiber PENNSYLVANIA, "Corrosion resistance of basalt fibers".
14. Mingchao W., Zuoguang Z., Yubin L., Min L. et Zhijie (2008), "Chemical Durability and Mechanical Properties of Alkali-proof Basalt Fiber and its Reinforced Epoxy Composites", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 27, pp.393-407.
15. ASTM E 2098-00, "Standard Test Method for Determining Tensile Breaking Strength of Glass Fiber Reinforcing Mesh for Use in Class PB Exterior Insulation and Finish Systems (EIFS), after Exposure to a Sodium Hydroxide Solution".
16. ASTM D 3039/D 3039M – 00, "Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials".